

MY LOVE POETRY (REVISED)

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Abstract

My Love Poetry is the premier collection of my five poems on the power of love as a metaphysical quest. Dominant themes of affection, heroism, destiny, spirituality, and timelessness are stylistically woven through tension and revelation. The imagery of time, covenant, prophecy, and light maintains the assurance of destiny's verdict in the search for love. The first poem, "A Quest in my Quest," reveals the poet's patience, anticipation, and endurance through time as he waits for the bride of his dreams. The second poem, "Invade My World," is an invitation to a transcendent future wife. This piece blends sacred longing with romantic quest. The third poem, "Come In," is an ode to the sovereign personality of love, weaving emotion with sacred heroism. The fourth poem, "To My Fatherly Mother," is a birthday tribute to the most powerful feminine figure, whom the poem describes as powerful as a man, differing only in the womb she possesses. This collection ends with a return to the original motif of the poet's thirst for true, sacred love and a destiny fulfilled, as the final poem, "Have My Quest," demonstrates. Overall, *My Love Poetry* articulates an appealing love dialogue between a masculine self and a feminine self, and then between humanity and Self, which is truth.

A QUEST IN MY QUEST!

O letter—let her enter! For creation
lingers unnamed—the one
made in my world unknown, blooming
a day before Sabbath!

Davidic spirit in her, ever recited in
Collecte's diary—in the innocence of
Time! How I face your gaze
In every phase, in the
Strength of weakness: taste of blaze
In every place—Quest of West, signs of
Time for the man of the moon!

I stand with patience armed as speed; —
I watch every light through the dark arc; —
Every syllable is a silence in my sacred diary: —
Nothing naughty.

What I haven't seen already sees
me, for the future curls behind
the future, and tomorrow is after tomorrow:
a time in time—in the span of my palm. I face
your gaze in every February feast. But
destined castles fade to shade, that the bride
of pride may wear the world's third bloom! I
transfer Him their burdens as if they were
dawns. But I pray fate to carve
upon our hearts the word that wove
our waves! For only

ETERNITY has neither a lowercase nor a period

INVADE MY WORLD

Cool the ember of my breath,
where healing halts at its rim. May
flame turn fame, and
let Easter whisper in winter;
every vein of mine grips dawn drowned—
the stars of tides fast faced.

Wander in, into my silence, through
the midst of my stone garden—
colored, sharp, flame-shaped sickle
of the meek Wise that sings
the Davidic wisdom in ages, with her
king's prophecy archived in her
tongue's library. On my May bed at midnight's
mirror, I see a flying future, leaving the flies
of her foes fried in fury! It is all grace:
The work of Word at work—and I

have to live with this blessedness all my day

COME IN!

Come in, O Welcome Itself, Kiss crowned
as King! Your rule is our will! No change
can change You! May
Darkness unmake its errors at the
thunder of Your verb.

Sciences found waves, prophets decode winds, yet
Your slip unseen through worlds' frequencies. The
sun is Your shadow: –and the fade of Your shade
keeps the noon running.

Descend, Maker of matter, to the
mortal You molded! Give weight to
wonder; translate grass into grace:
–Till all nations wash
their flags in Your psalms.

TO MY FATHERLY MOTHER

You are a Womb Man, Collectte,
a womb of wonder

I tread the garden of mind, press thought
through thought—a dome of trembling morphology—
to birth a syllable from my depth! But time
remains an unfaithful midwife.

Memory forgets its name.

And years confess their failure.

For how will

I remember to forget the one who
believes in the presence of my future,
to make life an Eldorado for mankind?

Collectte's friendly strictness—
with humorous technicality,
principled, seasoned, regulates
the tonicity of her spontaneously

gesticulated nuances: –in chastity
and chastisement. All honors
your honor in the assembly of your kind,
home and abroad.

When creations would flee for
freedom, all look forward to
seeing your efforts' true fruit—that you
gave a Christ in crisis. When they
will flee for free, you'll be remembered
by the alabaster of endurance.

HAVE MY QUEST

Clear like a mystery, popular like
the unsaid: Time blinks twice—
once for memory, once for the unknown.

Between them, we breathe; younger
than history, older than
future!

Our night is Your day, Sir, as our time
our dime! So find us where oblivion
grows ripe! —Feed Your field. ...

Buy it from grave! And sorrow? Let it
be unto Your foes—unto those who abhor
Your hope! Soak them in Your furnaces.

My thirst, a quest, kept in my quest: —
to exist in the pages of the scroll You inked,
to brush infinity's edge with a finite finger, and

touch life ... lives ... across the sea.

Rewrite me—the version of wonder You
never repeated: start a new history. Match my
destiny with a good perfect match, as destiny
finds us, in the real world we were made for—
—the truth I sought
for two hundred decades—ever to feast
on Your site ... archived in Mercy, kept
by unparalleled Truths.

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Bio

[David Achodo](#) is a PhD candidate and Graduate Teaching Associate in French at the University of Tennessee. A French, English, German, Fon, and Yoruba speaker, Achodo's research has embraced Translation Studies, Literature, Language Acquisition, Culture, and Artificial Intelligence. David Achodo is the Primary Organizer and Founding Member of the "World Languages and Cultures Graduate Student Association" at the University of Tennessee, who did excellent work in spearheading its formation. Also, as a [Poet](#), David Achodo is known for his thought-provoking, metaphysical poetry that invokes self-discovery and the exploration of the unknown Forces of life that regulate all existence.